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A STUDY OF VERB USED IN AN ENGLISH NEWS ONLINE WEBSITE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this independent study was to analyze the verbs used in an English learning website, BreakingNewsEnglish.com. The sample for the study consisted 40 news selected by simple random sampling. This case study analyzed two aspects of verb usage: transitive verb and intransitive verb. The conclusion based on the results as follows: 1) The transitive verb in the base form was used most frequently (40.41%) while present participle form was used the least frequently (6.79%). 2) The intransitive verb in the base form occurred most frequently (7.13%) whereas the verb in present participle form were used only (2.21%). In conclusion, in Breaking news used transitive verb more than intransitive verb all types, the most of percentages was transitive verb with 40.41% and the lowest percentages was intransitive verb in present participle with 2.21%. BreakingNewsEnglish.com refers to events that are currently developing and are unexpected, the base form of transitive verbs helpful instructions for users on the site are extremely basic, clear and simple instruction usually seem to be a good indication of thoughtful.

Keywords:

verb used analysis, English news, English learning Website.

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1. INTRODUCTION

English has firmly become the international language and more widely used in the world of communication and also in news that we read each day. It is not enough to know only about domestic news but we should also know about international news. BreakingNewsEnglish.com has headlines from news stories as they happen around the world each day, including variety of exercises, topical lessons and all skills. The site is interactive and has printable English lessons for classes and homework. There are answers at the end of each lesson; it's like an online classroom to attract people to learn English online. The writer uses contemporary vocabularies and the writing style of the English language owner that we can remember and use English Language. Therefore the verb usage at BreakingNewsEnglish.com is usually in the present simple, because verb is the word that shows the action of subject in sentences and changes the

meaning of sentences. Verbs also help other verbs for mood voice and tense. For these reasons and to enhance the student's ability in English Language and for use in and out of the classroom verbs are important.

The world has developed many new technologies and now, there are various forms of news available within a variety of languages. The news comes from many sources and the reports are presented in assorted styles. Breaking news has headlines from limited news stories as they happen around the world each day. There is a variety of exercises we can download and copy for classes or homework and can check answers at the end of the breaking news article; it's like a classroom to attract people to learn the English Language.

The native English speaking owner and writer uses contemporary English language vocabularies and writing styles. Therefore verbs at breaking news are mostly present simple, because the verb is the action word in a sentence and changes the meaning of sentences or helps another verb in mood voice and tense. For these reasons the researcher chose to focus on verbs because they enhance the ability in English language and students can use both in and away from the classroom.

New technology gives different forms of information to customers and the ability to easily search through the Internet (Poompuang, 2005). Technology makes gaining information comfortable and is the fastest and the most accessible way for receiving along a wide range. Although, you may be in a different country or continent you can still receive information rapidly. The internet and online services have has growing exponentially on a daily basis in all areas as a response to a rapidly increasing number of people needs (Ounsuwan, 2005). Many users explore internet to learn, chat and search for entertainment or news information.

In the older days, news letter writing only paper was used and was hard to carry. However, the introduction of the internet has provided a new passage of communication which is cheaper, faster and more efficient. Therefore, this case study aims to analyze the language of verb usage in BreakingNewsEnglish.com. There are various kinds of languages used for writing news to contribute to the great benefit for language learners in systemically using the word from grammar, phrases and sentences in the next level of language use.

Purpose of the Study: To analyze the types of English verbs frequency used, transitive and intransitive verbs in an online newspaper site entitled BreakingNewsEnglish.com.

Scope of the Study: This study covers the transitive and intransitive verbs of BreakingNewsEnglish.com. All 40 news items cover 4 forms of verbs, selected by the researcher. The finding consists of the breakdown of verbs used. The study focuses on transitive verbs and intransitive verbs that exist in the excerpts.

Limitation of the Study: Actually, there are many verbs used at BreakingNewsEnglish.com but some have low frequencies of occurrence. Therefore, merely two kinds of verbs that are frequently used in part of speech in English Language are analyzed in this case study and focusing on verb as part of speech from the 13th of September 2013 to 24th of June 2014 from BreakingNewsEnglish.com. In general, there are many verbs used as quotes and sources but only

two kinds of verbs used in part of speech in English language which occur in the collected data of this study. Consequently, the study focuses only on the frequency of transitive verbs and intransitive verbs sources are counted and analyzed table.

Significance of the study: It will be useful knowledge for students to use the findings so that they can better understand each news item at BreakingNewsEnglish.com. The findings are useful for English teachers who teach verbs, using news online as their teaching resources. The findings should be useful for people who are interested in English language and wish to improve their knowledge of the language.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data of this independent study based on the data collected from the news BreakingNewsEnglish.com from 13th of September 2013 to 24th of June 2014.

Materials: Download 40 news stories of lessons in seven levels above from Breakingnewsenglish.com, as follows:

- | | |
|---|----------------------------|
| 1. Women should have babies before 35 | 13th Sep, 2013 |
| 2. Blob fish are the ugliest animals | 17th Sep, 2013 |
| 3. Syria says it will destroy chemical weapons | 21st Sep, 2013 |
| 4. Scientists find gene that erases memories | 25th Sep, 2013 |
| 5. Jet-lag drug is a step closer | 7th Oct, 2013 |
| 6. Hunger affects one in eight people | 3rd Oct, 2013 |
| 7. EU wants change after Lampedusa deaths | 11th Oct, 2013 |
| 8. Education adviser attacks UK schools | 15th Oct, 2013 |
| 9. BBC plans 2,500 hours of World War I shows | 19 th Oct, 2013 |
| 10. More people think online dating is OK | 23 rd Oct, 2013 |
| 11. Japanese food to get UNESCO status | 27 th Oct, 2013 |
| 12. Britney Spears' music scares off pirates | 31 st Oct, 2013 |
| 13. Only 10% of OK engineering are woman | 6 th Nov, 2013 |
| 14. Better tables for beautiful people in Paris restaurants | 10 th Nov, 2013 |
| 15. "Invisible" helmet for cyclists invented | 14 th Nov, 2013 |
| 16. USA destroys 6,000kg of ivory | 18 th Nov, 2013 |
| 17. Kids run more slowly than 30 years ago | 22 nd Nov, 2013 |
| 18. Amazon.com testing drone delivery service | 4 th Dec, 2013 |
| 19. World mourns Nelson Mandela | 8 th Dec, 2013 |
| 20. Coldest temperature on Earth recorded | 12 th Dec, 2013 |
| 21. Beyonce releases a secret album | 16th Dec, 2013 |
| 22. Christmas becoming less religious in U.S. | 20th Dec, 2013 |
| 23. 2014 to be the best year ever | 1st Jan, 2014 |
| 24. Nearly 1 billion obese people in developing world | 5th Jan, 2014 |
| 25. Job hunter puts CV on billboard | 9 th Jan, 2014 |
| 26. Alternative medicine becoming popular in Bahrain | 13th Jan, 2014 |
| 27. British Museum has most successful year | 17th Jan, 2014 |
| 28. Smog makes Beijing put sunrise on giant TVs | 21st Jan, 2014 |

29. Almost no poor countries by 2035	25th Jan, 2014
30. Online dining latest craze in South Korea	29th Jan, 2014
31. UK to ban smoking in cars with kids	14th Feb, 2014
32. Wikipedia may become million-page book	22nd Feb, 2014
33. Couple finds \$10 million of coins in garden	28th Feb, 2014
34. One in three EU women experienced violence	8 th Mar, 2014
35. Panasonic China staff to get “pollution pay”	16 th Mar, 2014
36. Turkey court says Twitter helps free speech	5 th Apr, 2014
37. Too much jogging could shorten your life	9 th Apr, 2014
38. Companies still fixing Heart bleed bug	17 th Apr, 2014
39. Tourist deported for Buddha tattoo	25 th Apr, 2014
40. New prayer house for three religions	24 th Jun, 2014

Data Collection and data analysis: The researchers gather the news from the website BreakingNewsEnglish.com from 13th of September 2013 to 24th of June 2014 as the sources of information for this study. Then, select the news from BreakingNewsEnglish.com. After that type the 40 news to be analyzed. The analysis part of verbs data in the news will be carried out in the following steps: 1) analyze the verb of sources used often from BreakingNewsEnglish.com 2) classify of verbs into transitive verb and intransitive verb 3) type the 40 statements and store them on the computer 4) find frequencies group of verb in transitive verb and intransitive into four forms; base form, -s form, past form, present form and present participle form. 5) write a final report.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Breaking news uses transitive verb of base form in a total of 238 words with 40.41%. Transitive verb of -s form in a total of 56 words with 9.51%. Transitive verb of past form in a total of 156 words with 26.1%. Transitive verb of present participle form in a total of 40 words with 7.13%. In contrast, breaking news uses intransitive verb of base form in a total of 40 words with 6.79%. Intransitive verb of -s form in a total of 15 words with 2.55%. Intransitive verb of past form in a total of 31 words with 5.26%.. Intransitive verb of present participle form in a total of 13 words with 2.21%. Based on the results of the study the news writers want to tell a long connected story to readers “newspapers should use only simple sentences” (Yan, 2005) because of the writer want to tell the readers update news every days and makes clearly understand the meaning of word and context for receiver, sentence structure and page design should help readers move through the news quickly Meksujit (2002) with the competition between advertisers and editorial today. The writer should write persuasive in order to catch reader’s attention Sangsuwan (1997) and understand every sentences clearly such as base form, -s form, past form and present participle form. Wren & Martin (1993) said “The language you choose to express your thoughts is an extremely important element of the writing process because only through the words you choose and the way you arrange them can your reader understand your thoughts about the topic”. In other words, whereas writer use and choose words should consider from several approaches. In conclusion, in Breaking news used transitive verb more than intransitive verb all types, the most of percentages was transitive verb with 40.41% and the lowest percentages was intransitive verb in present participle with 2.21%. Because breakingnewsenglish.com refers to events that are currently developing and are unexpected, the base form of transitive verbs helpful instructions

for users on the site are extremely basic, clear and simple instruction usually seem to be a good indication of thoughtful.

4. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

This case study was analyzed in two parts of verbs as an analysis of vocabulary verb used in transitive verb and intransitive verb and an analysis of using word choices. In the result of the four categories of verbs; base form, -s form, past form and present participle form to show that base forms were most frequently used in transitive verb and intransitive verb and found that transitive verbs were more popularly used than the intransitive verb. Comparing the frequencies of using base form between transitive verb and intransitive verb, those of transitive verb were 40.41% while intransitive verb is 6.79%. As regards the frequencies of occurrences in both of verbs; for transitive verb, past form (26.15%), -s form (9.51%) and present participle form (7.13%) respectively. For intransitive verb occur at significantly different as follow: past form (5.26%), -s form (2.55%) and present participle (2.21%) respectively. Based on all word frequencies, the study shows that past form “said” is the word that is most frequently used 10.69%, the second rank is the base form “want” was used 3.05% and the third rank is “like” was used 2.71%. The frequency of word category used for transitive verb and intransitive verb from 40 online news, “BreakingnewsEnglish.com” of 589 words used. The frequently word used of transitive verb in total 490 words were 238 words of base form, 56 words of -s form, 156 words of past form, 40 words of present participle form. The frequently word used of intransitive verb in total 99 words; 40 words for base form, 15 words for -s form, 31 words of past form, 13 words of present participle form. Finally, there are figures of verbs used in writing BreakingnewsEnglish.com which are differentiated from the tropes on the purpose of the writer and situation, that is transitive verb used most frequently were 238 words for base form , while the least frequent in intransitive verb were 13 words for present participle form.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings in this study are benefits for learners and whose interests in English Language because clearly of words to use and understand, saving of time for planning and saving the money for learning English language. The analysis is useful for learners to increase understanding and permanent of memorize English words and development English skill in listening, reading and writing skill. This independent study is useful for those who would like to teach English language as their teaching resource. A translator who translates international news into the Thai language can use these as a guideline for translating into Thai newspapers. A study of Grammatical English Language in breakingnewsenglish.com which studies all of interactive and printable English lessons 7 levels. A study of Grammatical English Language used in news in other website such as VOA, BBC News, Bangkok Post, or News-The big project.

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7. REFERENCES

- [1] Meksujit, S. *Grammatical Structures Used in Business Sections of the Nation and the Bangkok Post: A Case Study. Master of Arts Thesis, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology North Bangkok, 2002: 20-41.*
- [2] Ounsuwan, K. *A Genre of Language Used in E-Greeting Cards on the Internet. Master of Arts Thesis. King Mongkut's Institute of Technology North Bangkok, 2005:1-35.*
- [3] Poompuang, K. *English Usage in Perfume Advertising from the Web Page: A Case Study. Master of Art Thesis. King Mongkut's Institute of Technology North Bangkok, 2005: 5-42.*
- [4] Sangsuwan, P. *An Analysis of the Language Used in Action and Comedy Movie Handbills. Master of Arts Thesis. Assumption University, 1997: 4.*
- [5] Wren, P. C. & Martin, H. *High School English Grammar and Composition. India, Rajendra Ravindra Printers. 1993:33-50.*
- [6] Yan, L. *English Language Movies for the Classroom. China, Beijing Normal University, n.p: 2005.*